

EFFICIENT DRYING USING INLINE MEASUREMENT TECHNOLOGY

Residual moisture measurement for cost-saving process optimisation in the manufacturing industry

WHERE IS MOISTURE SENSOR TECHNOLOGY APPLIED?

Moisture sensors are ideally suited for drying processes in various industries such as food, starch production and wood processing.

The advanced inline technology enables precise quality and process control through exact moisture measurements. At the same time, important chemical parameters such as protein and fat content, as well as the progress of reactions, can be detected.

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF THE INLINE SENSOR TECHNOLOGY?

- Direct and non-contact measurement of product moisture
- Simple and cost-effective measurement of chemical parameters
- Improved process understanding through new insights into the drying process
- Quality optimisation: neither over-drying nor underdrying of the product
- Cost reduction through energy savings
- Contribution to sustainability (sustainability reporting)
- CO₂ reduction

THAT SOUNDS PERFECT! WHAT'S NEXT?

Set-up an initial consultation appointment with the NEFI team!

Step 1: We will analyse your situation in an initial meeting.

Step 2: A cost-effective feasibility study provides certainty about the implementability.

Step 3: Together, we adapt the existing technology precisely to the process requirements.

Step 4: We install and commission the solution and provide ongoing support and maintenance during operation.

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